

Canine Exposure

Dr. Rohan Khare

A 14 year old male patient reported to the dept with an impacted canine. On examination, canine exposure using LASER was decided. Soft tissue diode laser was set to gingivectomy mode (0.8 W setting) at continuous pulsation mode. The tissue was excised and COE Pak was given. Patient was recalled after 10 days. On examination, the healing was proper and further orthodontic treatment was initiated.

Pre Operative

Intra Operative

Post Operative

